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High Level Digital Skills in Europe

Grew by 14.28% in DESI countries between 2016 and 2021

The Digital Economy and Society Index-DESI calculates the value of Advanced Skills and Development in European countries. The data are available between 2016 and 2021. The variable "Advanced Skills and Development" is made up of a set of variables or "ICT Specialists", "Female ICT Specialists", "Enterprise Providing ICT Training", "ICT graduates".

AdvancedSkillsAndDevelopment_{it}

$$= a_1 + b_1(\text{ICTSpecialists})_{it} + b_2(\text{FemaleICTSpecialists})_{it} \\ + b_3(\text{EnterprisesProvidingICTTraining})_{it} + b_4(\text{ICTGraduates})_{it}$$

Ranking of European countries by value of high-level digital skills. Finland is in first place for the value of the digital skills of high-level with a value of 32.88, followed by Sweden with a value of 28.54, and Estonia with a value of 27.70. In the middle of the table there are Malta with a value of 20.71, followed by Latvia with a value of 20.25 and Spain with a value of 19.79 units. Greece closes the ranking with a value of 17.01 units, Poland with a value of 16.79 and Italy with a value of 14.90 units. The average in 2021 was equal to an amount of 21.16.

Ranking of countries by change in high-level technological skills between 2016 and 2021. Lithuania ranks first in terms of the value of the change in high-level technological skills between 2016 and 2021 with a value equal to 34.83% to an amount of 4.84 units, followed by Estonia with a value equal to 32.53% equal to an amount of 6.80 units and Slovakia with a value equal to 28.86% equal to an amount of 4, 08 units. In the middle of the table there are Croatia with an amount of 15.11% equal to an amount of 2.58 units, followed by Ireland with a value equal to 14.47 units equal to an amount of 3.46%, followed by Italy with a value of 14.36% prior to an amount of 1.87 units. Austria closes the ranking with a value equal to 1.18% equal to an amount of 0.24 units, followed by Cyprus with a variation equal to -2.06% equal to an amount of -0.38 units, followed by from Malta with a variation of -14.32% equal to an amount of -3.46 units. On average for European countries, the value of the variation between 2016 and 2021 was equal to an amount of 14.28% equal to an amount of 2.49 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering is carried out below using the k-Means algorithm optimized using the Silhouette coefficient. Two different clusters have been identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Czech Republic, Portugal, Lithuania, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Poland, Cyprus, Italy, Greece, France, Croatia, Spain, Latvia, Bulgaria, Netherlands, Slovenia, Belgium.
- Cluster 2: Sweden, Ireland, Denmark, Estonia, Malta, Finland, Luxembourg, Austria, Germany.

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By calculating the value of the median of the countries analyzed, it results that the value of cluster 2-C2 is equal to 25.72 while the value of cluster 1-C1 is equal to 19.16. It follows therefore that $C2 = 25.72 > C1 = 19.16$. Considering the distribution of high-level technological skills, it is clear that the countries of central and northern Europe tend to have very high values in terms of high-level technological skills compared to the countries of Central-Southern Europe and Eastern Europe. However, the clustering achieved through the maximization of the Silhouette coefficient offers an excessively simplistic view of the relationship-contrast between Central-Northern Europe and Southern-Eastern Europe. It follows therefore that a further tool is used, namely the Elbow method. Using the Elbow method there is evidently a three-way clustering. Redoing the calculations through the application of the clustering algorithm, there are three clusters identified as follows:

- Cluster 1: Poland, Slovakia, Italy, Greece, Hungary, Lithuania, Portugal, Czech Republic;
- Cluster 2: Slovenia, Bulgaria, the Netherlands, Spain, Belgium, Latvia, Germany, France, Croatia, Cyprus, Austria, Romania;
- Cluster 3: Sweden, Ireland, Denmark, Finland, Estonia, Malta, Luxembourg.

Through the application of the optimal number of clusters achieved through the Elbow method, a more composite dimension of the European dimension results in terms of distribution of high-level technological skills. By calculating the median value of the individual clusters, it results that the value of cluster 1-C1 is equal to 17.7, while the median value of cluster 2-C2 is equal to 20.97 and the median value of cluster 3-C3 is equal at 27.41. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, i.e. $C3 = 27.41 > C2 = 20.97 > C1 = 17.7$. By applying this new clustering rule, a greater explanatory capacity is obtained. In fact, looking at the map of 3-way clustering, a structure emerges where the countries of Northern Europe, especially Scandinavian countries, dominate over the countries of Central Europe, and the latter over the countries of South-East Europe, except for Romania and Hungary which instead participate in the second cluster.

Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. A network analysis is presented using the Manhattan distance. The analysis shows the presence of three network structures, two of which are complex, i.e. they have a number of linkages higher than 2, and one is simplified or have a number of linkages equal to 2. There is a complex network structure consisting of Slovenia, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Spain, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Czech Republic. In particular:

- Slovenia has a link with Bulgaria with a value of 0.34;
- Bulgaria has a link with Slovenia with a value of 0.34, with Croatia with a value of 0.37 and with Spain with a value of 0.25;
- Croatia has a link with Bulgaria equal to an amount of 0.37, with France with a value equal to 0.37;
- France has a link with Croatia equal to a value of 0.37 and with Spain with a value of 0.3;
- Spain has a link with France equal to an amount of 0.3, with Bulgaria with a value equal to 0.25, with Latvia with a value equal to 0.38 and with Cyprus with a value equal to 0, 31;
- Latvia has a link with Spain with a value of 0.38;
- Cyprus has a link with Spain equal to a value of 0.31 and with Romania equal to a value of 0.33;
- Romania has a link with Cyprus equal to an amount of 0.33 and with the Czech Republic with a value of 0.38;
- The Czech Republic has a link with Romania equal to an amount of 0.38.

There is also a further complex network structure between Italy, Greece, and Poland. Particularly:

- Italy has a connection with Greece with a value of 0.31 and with Poland with a value of 0.1;
- Poland has a link with Greece equal to a value of 0.33 and with Italy a link equal to 0.1;
- Greece has a link with Italy for an amount of 0.31, and with Poland for a value of 0.33.

In addition, there is a further simplified network structure between Ireland and Sweden which reciprocally have a link with a value of 0.37.

Conclusions. In summary, it is possible to underline that the value of high-level digital skills grew between 2016 and 2021 by an amount equal to 14.28%. However, there are quite serious conditions in Europe that highlight how complex the approach to digital transformation is even for industrialized countries. For example, Italy ranks last in value of high-level digital skills in 2021. Furthermore, Poland also has a low level of high-level digital skills and this condition conflicts with geographical proximity with Germany and other countries of Northern Europe and Scandinavia which, on the other hand, have high levels of digital capacity. It therefore follows that access to high-level digital skills is not a necessary consequence of a high level of industrialization - as in the case of Italy, or of the geographical proximity to areas of high economic and industrial growth - as in the case of Poland. On the contrary, to create the conditions for high-level digital skills, it is necessary to create specific economic and industrial policies that take into consideration first of all the formation of human capital and, secondly, create the conditions for the prosperity of high-tech companies, also thanks to a favorable institutional environment.

Declarations

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Appendix

Rank	Countries	★ 2021	Rank	Countries	★ 2021
★ 1	<i>Finland</i>	☆ 32,88	★ 15	<i>Croatia</i>	☆ 19,69
★ 2	<i>Sweden</i>	☆ 28,54	★ 16	<i>France</i>	☆ 19,67
★ 3	<i>Estonia</i>	☆ 27,70	★ 17	<i>Portugal</i>	☆ 19,67
★ 4	<i>Ireland</i>	☆ 27,41	★ 18	<i>Bulgaria</i>	☆ 19,35
★ 5	<i>Denmark</i>	☆ 25,72	★ 19	<i>Romania</i>	☆ 18,97
★ 6	<i>Luxembourg</i>	☆ 24,79	★ 20	<i>Lithuania</i>	☆ 18,74
★ 7	<i>Netherlands</i>	☆ 22,31	★ 21	<i>Czechia</i>	☆ 18,72
★ 8	<i>Germany</i>	☆ 21,38	★ 22	<i>Slovakia</i>	☆ 18,21
★ 9	<i>Belgium</i>	☆ 21,32	★ 23	<i>Cyprus</i>	☆ 17,85
★ 10	<i>Austria</i>	☆ 20,97	★ 24	<i>Hungary</i>	☆ 17,18
★ 11	<i>Slovenia</i>	☆ 20,80	★ 25	<i>Greece</i>	☆ 17,01
★ 12	<i>Malta</i>	☆ 20,71	★ 26	<i>Poland</i>	☆ 16,79
★ 13	<i>Latvia</i>	☆ 20,25	★ 27	<i>Italy</i>	☆ 14,90
★ 14	<i>Spain</i>	☆ 19,79			

Competenze di Alto Livello in Europa nel 2021. Fonte: DESI.

Variazione delle competenze tecnologiche di alto livello tra il 2016 ed il 2021. Fonte: DESI INDEX

Rank	Countries	Vas Ass	Var Per	Rank	Countries	Vas Ass	Var Per
1	Lithuania	★ 4,84	★ 34,83	15	Denmark	★ 2,94	★ 12,89
2	Estonia	★ 6,80	★ 32,52	16	Belgium	★ 2,43	★ 12,89
3	Slovakia	★ 4,08	★ 28,86	17	Hungary	★ 1,96	★ 12,88
4	Poland	★ 3,59	★ 27,21	18	Finland	★ 3,04	★ 10,18
5	Netherlands	★ 4,74	★ 26,94	19	Spain	★ 1,41	★ 7,65
6	Portugal	★ 3,86	★ 24,43	20	Latvia	★ 1,40	★ 7,40
7	Luxembourg	★ 4,76	★ 23,76	21	Romania	★ 1,31	★ 7,39
8	Sweden	★ 4,76	★ 20,03	22	Slovenia	★ 1,26	★ 6,45
9	Greece	★ 2,80	★ 19,70	23	Germany	★ 1,14	★ 5,65
10	France	★ 2,62	★ 15,35	24	Bulgaria	★ 0,82	★ 4,45
11	Czechia	★ 2,48	★ 15,30	25	Austria	★ 0,24	★ 1,18
12	Croatia	★ 2,58	★ 15,11	26	Cyprus	★ -0,38	★ -2,06
13	Ireland	★ 3,46	★ 14,47	27	Malta	★ -3,46	★ -14,32
14	Italy	★ 1,87	★ 14,36				

Variazione Assoluta del valore delle competenze tecnologiche di alto livello tra il 2016 ed il 2021. Fonte: DESI INDEX

Variazione Percentuale delle competenze tecnologiche di alto livello tra il 2016 ed il 2021. Fonte: DESI INDEX

Clusterization. C2>C1

Clusterizzazione. C3>C2>C1.

	2021	Countries	Cluster
1	20.9698	Austria	C2
2	21.3196	Belgium	C2
3	19.3501	Bulgaria	C2
4	19.6876	Croatia	C2
5	17.8519	Cyprus	C2
6	18.7231	Czechia	C1
7	25.7172	Denmark	C3
8	27.7020	Estonia	C3
9	32.8780	Finland	C3
10	19.6707	France	C2
11	21.3759	Germany	C2
12	17.0067	Greece	C1
13	17.1785	Hungary	C1
14	27.4064	Ireland	C3
15	14.8976	Italy	C1
16	20.2504	Latvia	C2
17	18.7357	Lithuania	C1
18	24.7862	Luxembourg	C3
19	20.7082	Malta	C3
20	22.3136	Netherlands	C2
21	16.7922	Poland	C1
22	19.6700	Portugal	C1
23	18.9668	Romania	C2
24	18.2133	Slovakia	C1
25	20.8045	Slovenia	C2
26	19.7867	Spain	C2
27	28.5409	Sweden	C3

Countries	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★ 20,73	★ 22,14	★ 21,07	★ 21,34	★ 20,65	★ 20,97
Belgium	☆ 18,89	☆ 18,21	★ 20,48	★ 21,78	★ 21,88	★ 21,32
Bulgaria	☆ 18,53	☆ 18,40	☆ 18,64	★ 19,92	☆ 19,38	☆ 19,35
Croatia	☆ 17,10	☆ 17,18	☆ 18,11	★ 20,44	☆ 19,33	★ 19,69
Cyprus	☆ 18,23	☆ 18,51	☆ 17,27	☆ 18,26	☆ 18,13	☆ 17,85
Czechia	☆ 16,24	☆ 16,37	☆ 16,53	☆ 17,78	☆ 18,24	☆ 18,72
Denmark	★ 22,78	★ 23,47	★ 23,14	★ 23,72	★ 24,81	★ 25,72
Estonia	★ 20,90	★ 21,72	★ 23,40	★ 25,15	★ 26,04	★ 27,70
Finland	★ 29,84	★ 29,31	★ 30,14	★ 29,04	★ 30,29	★ 32,88
France	☆ 17,05	☆ 17,77	☆ 18,14	☆ 18,60	★ 20,04	★ 19,67
Germany	★ 20,23	★ 20,29	★ 20,25	★ 21,00	★ 21,62	★ 21,38
Greece	☆ 14,21	☆ 13,40	☆ 13,16	☆ 13,77	☆ 15,36	☆ 17,01
Hungary	☆ 15,22	☆ 16,12	☆ 15,43	☆ 15,37	☆ 15,77	☆ 17,18
Ireland	★ 23,94	★ 26,24	★ 26,40	★ 25,32	★ 27,00	★ 27,41
Italy	☆ 13,03	☆ 13,35	☆ 14,02	☆ 14,69	☆ 15,19	☆ 14,90
Latvia	☆ 18,85	☆ 18,85	☆ 18,43	☆ 16,70	★ 20,00	★ 20,25
Lithuania	☆ 13,90	☆ 15,68	☆ 16,65	☆ 16,84	☆ 17,66	☆ 18,74
Luxembourg	★ 20,03	★ 22,34	★ 21,90	★ 22,70	★ 24,66	★ 24,79
Malta	★ 24,17	★ 21,49	★ 21,68	★ 24,76	★ 21,51	★ 20,71
Netherlands	☆ 17,58	☆ 18,94	★ 19,79	★ 20,48	★ 21,58	★ 22,31
Poland	☆ 13,20	☆ 13,80	☆ 14,20	☆ 14,81	☆ 15,36	☆ 16,79
Portugal	☆ 15,81	☆ 16,08	☆ 15,17	☆ 16,00	☆ 18,59	★ 19,67
Romania	☆ 17,66	☆ 17,43	☆ 16,89	☆ 17,10	☆ 17,54	☆ 18,97
Slovakia	☆ 14,13	☆ 13,83	☆ 14,93	☆ 15,37	☆ 17,09	☆ 18,21
Slovenia	☆ 19,54	☆ 19,10	☆ 19,21	★ 20,04	★ 20,66	★ 20,80
Spain	☆ 18,38	☆ 18,48	☆ 18,23	☆ 18,63	☆ 19,47	★ 19,79
Sweden	★ 23,78	★ 24,49	★ 25,71	★ 25,86	★ 27,49	★ 28,54

